

**THE PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN
INDIA: A REVIEW USING SCHWAB'S 'CURRICULUM COMMONPLACE'
FRAMEWORK**

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Abstract

This literature review investigates the problems and challenges in L2 teaching and learning in India in the last decade. Given the structure and diversity of the Indian education system, in-depth studies at the micro level and regular and continuous synthesis of data are required for a realistic understanding of the problems and challenges in ELT so that educators, policymakers and administrators can improve the quality of L2 teaching and learning. The two research questions posed were: What recurring challenges and problems in ELT in India are reported? And “What do these challenges and problems reveal about the status of ELT in India?” Joseph Schwab’s curriculum commonplace framework, namely, subject matter, learner, teacher, milieu, and curriculum-making, was adapted to collect and evaluate the data. The review found that poorly prepared teaching materials, teacher incompetency in terms of knowledge of content and methods, poor student preparedness and motivation, poor policies, cultural diversity and the huge urban-rural divide, and imbalanced and flawed curricula that do not promote language proficiency for employability to be the core problems and challenges in ELT. The research then argues that the findings indicate fundamental challenges and problems in how L2 is taught and learnt. It then suggests that radical shifts in vision, approach, policies and implementation are required to overcome these problems and challenges.

Keywords:

ELT-teaching content, ELT-Learner-Motivation, ELT-teacher incompetence, ELT-learning-context, ELT-curriculum, ELT challenges and problems.

Introduction

Various reports and studies of English in India during British rule raise questions about the quality of teaching and learning English as a second language (L2). Barring a few elite English medium schools, the medium of instruction was the vernacular in most government schools during the British times (Nurullah & Naik, 1943; Vennela & Smith, 2019). Other studies (Mathew, 2017; Surya, 2013; Vennela & Smith, 2019) report that during the British times, English was the worst taught subject for the following reasons: teachers' incompetence to correct pronunciation and writing, use of unsuitable lecture methods to teach English, absence of systematic instruction in English, students lacking in the opportunity to speak to or listen to those who spoke English well, faulty pronunciation, failure to use correct idioms and language, and the inability to write an original composition. Furthermore, learning outcomes of L2 during British times were poor and continued to be so in the independent Indian education system (Dixit & Padwad, 2018).

The status of English Language Teaching (ELT) did not improve drastically even decades after India gained independence from the British. The role of English itself was debated in independent India, and hence its teaching lacked direction (R. K. Gupta, 1995). Though the political turmoil after independence was characterised by nationalism, anti-English sentiments, and the nationwide move to make Hindi the national language, people still learnt English in Schools and colleges but did not speak it in society (Dixit & Padwad, 2018). During and after the debate over Hindi being made the national language of India (Aneesh, 2010; Khare, 2002; Mathew, 2017; S. S. Rao, 2008; V. K. R. Rao, 1978),

inadequate policies have paralysed the ELT in India (Abilasha & Ilankumaran, 2018; Anderson & Lightfoot, 2019; Mathew, 2017). Regional rivalries for language domination, public opinion in favour of English, the inability to design English courses to cater to the needs of students from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds, and teaching English in complete isolation from the native language and student's cultural context, characterise this period (R. K. Gupta, 1995). The overall impact of policy paralysis was poor L2 learning outcomes.

This literature review investigates the problems and challenges in L2 teaching and learning in India in the last decade, from 2010-2020. Given the enormous structure and diversity of the Indian education system in terms of cultural contexts, learners and instructors, in-depth studies at the micro level and regular and continuous synthesis of data are required to obtain a realistic picture of the status of ELT. By synthesising research findings from multiple and diverse educational contexts and discussing and comparing the findings against the established parameters of teaching and learning, this study will also give insights into the status of ELT in India. Such an investigation will help to understand the nature of issues, their prevalence, and their causes. The two research questions are: *What challenges and problems in ELT in India are reported? What do these challenges and problems reveal about the status of ELT in India?*

Research Framework

The American curriculum theorist Joseph Schwab's (1973) five curriculum commonplaces is a useful framework to investigate the field, organize the data and interpret the findings. The five curriculum commonplaces are subject matter, learners, the milieu, teachers, and curriculum making. Schwab proposed this framework to identify the types of experiences or expertise required by those who undertake effective curriculum revision in schools.

The subject matter is the scholarly material translated into the curriculum. How much time and energy should be set apart for a subject, how much of it should be taught, the selections to be made for different children, different versions and emphasis made in the interests of the needs and abilities of different children, and the inclusion of the best or good or satisfying to the learners as a child, as a human being and as a citizen are important considerations while selecting and implementing the subject matter. A curriculum material should be scrutinised for its purpose, the discipline from which it originates, and the discipline in which it makes the student competent. Utility for the community, appropriateness to the age and experience of the learners, the preparedness of the teachers and teacher training possibilities, and use of curriculum at the service of the students rather than curriculum conforming to the nature of the subject are other important considerations when a scholarly matter is translated into the curriculum.

According to Schwab, teachers are important mediators of learning for students. The beliefs, knowledge, capabilities, and lack of abilities of the teachers will influence the learning process in indescribable ways. Furthermore, flexibility and readiness to learn new material and methods of teaching, ways they relate to children, to one another and superiors, their feelings about themselves, their background, biases, and political affiliations are factors that will have an impact on the curriculum implementation.

The learners are the beneficiaries of the curriculum operation. Schwab observes that the learners' age, knowledge level, readiness to learn, difficulty in learning, ease of learning, aspirations, and anxieties should be considered while forming the curriculum.

Milieu, the fourth component in the 'Curriculum Commonplace' is the "nested, expanding contexts in which learning and teaching occur, including the classroom, the school, and wider community". The contexts may be many, nesting within each other. These contexts range from the very classroom of the students to the family, neighbourhood, religion, and culture in which they find themselves.

The final component is the curriculum-making process. It is the coordination of the four bodies of experience, namely, subject matter, teachers, learners, and milieu, to create a workable curriculum model. The coordinator animates the other representatives having expertise in one or many fields such

as subject matter, learner, teacher, and context. In curriculum making, each representative of a body of experience must familiarise themselves with the experience of others and the relevance of these fundamentally different experiences. The final curriculum is a balanced combination of these bodies of experiences. In such a curriculum-making process, if the coordinator is not experienced enough, each representative will tend to project the structure of one's discipline as the correct model for the curriculum under construction. The concerns raised by each representative should find accommodation in the curriculum but not at the cost of completely ignoring the concerns of the other representatives.

1. Methodology and Procedure

The latest findings from the Indian ELT context were investigated to understand the problems and challenges. Only those articles investigating ELT published after 2010 in the Indian context were selected. To ensure the objectivity and reliability of the data collected, research articles with a transparent research methodology, such as research problem, objectives/question, literature review, analysis, and conclusions – were given priority. Reports by government agencies, book chapters, and reports of interviews with experts were selected occasionally. The articles reviewed were sourced mainly from journals indexed in the Scopus and Web of Science list, UGC CARE list and a few other national and international journals. The databases from where they were sourced are ERIC, JStore, Google Scholar and Research Gate. Terms such as "problems and challenges to ELT in India," "pedagogical problems and challenges to ELT in India", "ELT teachers: problems and challenges," "students of ELT: problems and challenges," "ELT materials: problems and challenges," "ELT evaluation and challenges," "ELT and curriculum challenges," and "ELT policy and challenges" were used to locate the relevant articles.

3. Findings

3.1. Subject matter-related challenges

The subject matter is the scholarly material translated into the curriculum. The two major barriers identified under subject matter-related challenges are flawed content and teaching methods.

Jayanthi (2011) found that the teaching materials were ungraded in terms of vocabulary, subject matter, language, style, exercises, glossary, and relevance. Anjaneyulu (2014) discovered that writers did not pilot textbooks to ensure validity and reliability. Furthermore, he also found that the textbooks did not have provisions for developing LSRW skills and learner autonomy. Dash (2015) found that the syllabus was not updated for more than a decade in one of the Universities with 101 affiliated colleges in India. These textbooks lacked authentic language and were dominated by obsolete Grammar Translation Methods (GTM). Many educators and researchers (Geetha, 2015; Jose, 2013; Lakshmi, 2016; Sinha, 2014; Sreehari, 2012) have recommended the use of authentic teaching materials, such as newspapers, web-based materials, magazines, stories, jokes, pictures of exciting topics, movies, music, television soap operas, Facebook, Twitter, chatting, texting, literary books, and comics in place of conventional ones.

Flawed teaching methods are pointed out as another barrier. The obsolete GTM method of teaching language continues in a large number of schools and colleges (Bhattacharya, 2013; Gupta, 2013; Kapoor, 2013; Renukadevi, 2013). Teaching English as a subject goes against the latest understandings based on theory and practice that language classes should develop the communication skills of learners (Graves & Garton, 2017). The overall approach to teaching English only as a subject is still a dominant practice in many schools and colleges in India (Jena & Mishra, 2020; Saikia, 2013; Sreehari, 2012; Tyagi, 2015; Vijay, 2014). Furthermore, many studies (Kapoor, 2013; R. Thakur, 2020; Vishwanath & Srilakshmi, 2016; Viswanath & Mohanty, 2019) report that teaching English only as a subject, inability of students to relate to the content of the textbooks and the absence of interaction in the classroom demotivate many students from learning L2.

3.2. Teacher-centric barriers

Teacher-centric barriers to L2 teaching and learning in the Indian context revolve mostly around teacher beliefs and the knowledge of content and teaching methods. Studies (Piller & Skillings, 2005; Shinde & Karekatti, 2012) have found that teachers did not possess the correct notions concerning the principles and methods of teaching language. Lack of content knowledge (Xavier & Vijayakumar, 2019), knowledge of methods (Kale, 2020; Saikia, 2013), knowledge of the advanced methods and concepts of teaching such as CLT, ESP and English for Employability (Clement & Murugavel, 2015) even by the teachers at the college levels ail ELT in the country. What lies at the roots of all the teacher-centric barriers is the inability to understand the needs of the students (Renukadevi, 2013). Renukadevi (2013) also notes that the absence of language use outside the classroom and the lack of confidence to speak L2 equally affect the teachers

Many scholars point to the inadequate teacher training programmes in the country as the cause of such poor teacher beliefs and knowledge. Kaur and Bhangu (2015) observe that while a B.Ed or M.Ed is required to teach in the school, anyone with NET (National Eligibility Test) certificate and a master's degree can teach English at the UG level. Besides, many schools and colleges have a total absence of job training, refresher courses, and orientation on change of syllabi for the teachers (Saikia, 2013). The descriptive study by Sharma (2013) reveals the huge gap in the competency level between urban and rural EL teachers in India. It is particularly significant considering the huge number of students and teachers in rural areas.

3.3. Learner-Centric Barriers

According to Schwab, intellectual and psychological student preparedness plays a significant role in the effectiveness of the teaching-learning process. Studies (Anil, 2015; Sujatha, 2014; Vijay, 2014) have found that students' perception regarding the use of learning a language, poor language grooming by former teachers and lack of right instruction by teachers either create or deplete motivation to learn L2. The inability of the learners to adapt to different approaches and methods employed by different teachers (Walia, 2012), heterogeneity in terms of previous training, medium of instruction, style of learning, and language environment (Gaur, 2008), varied proficiency levels (Gupta, 2013) lack of confidence to speak out in the classroom and engage in classroom discussion (Vishwanath & Srilakshmi, 2016; Xavier & Vijayakumar, 2019), and the lack of opportunities to write articles, stories and essays, and the absence of guidance (Kumar, 2020) are also factors that act as barriers to L2 learning.

3.4. Contextual Barriers

The two significant contextual barriers to L2 learning are inadequate policy and infrastructure. Mohanty et al. (2010) report that in the absence of sufficient emphasis and well-rounded policies, especially after the first few decades after independence, English was taught only as a subject in India. Roy (2017) sheds light upon a contradiction in the current policy of the government that competitive exams are in English while the curriculum is transacted in the vernacular in the state school. Furthermore, there is no emphasis on language proficiency at the college level in many higher education institutions, while college students are required to be adept at communication skills (Gupta, 2013). Sharma (2013) found that there was no language policy at all at the state level and that the teachers who had neither studied English nor trained to teach English taught EL.

Adding to the woes of policy paralysis are the infrastructural deficiencies. Rapid expansion without proper planning (U. N. Singh, 2017), lack of teacher support and mechanism for teacher enhancement, lack of funding and absence of technology in primary education (Sharma, 2013), lack of provision of newspapers, magazines, journals, computers, audio-visual (Saikia, 2013), lack of technological equipment and space (Walia, 2012) are indicated as infrastructure related drawbacks paralysing ELT. Yet another significant contextual barrier is the huge rural-urban divide and the cultural and linguistic diversity for which India is known. India is a sub-continent itself with diverse geography, hundreds of

languages, and many cultures and hence, the diversity of experience students come with to the schools is pointed out as a contextual barrier. In such classrooms, a single methodology of teaching will not benefit students (U. N. Singh, 2017; Vishwanath & Srilakshmi, 2016). The vast majority of the learners in the rural areas, who study mainly in the government-run vernacular medium schools, are disadvantageously placed to learn English as they lag behind in access to the latest technology, absence of language labs, computers, LCD projectors, tape recorder, and microphone (P. A. Rao, 2018; Sharma, 2013; D. K. Thakur, 2019; Vivek & Prakat, 2018).

3.5. Curriculum-centric Barriers

A robust curriculum is a fundamental requirement for an effective teaching-learning process, as Schwab postulates. The inadequacies in the curriculum can be manifested in poor teaching and learning outcomes, and such inadequacies can be attributed to deficient coordination in the curriculum-making process.

Wrong notions that policymakers, educators and administrators have about English and how it is to be taught, can manifest in poor teaching-learning outcomes. Jeyraj (2017) observes that when educationalists, administrators, and teachers themselves assume English as the language of the West imposed on India, it can give rise to various methodological dilemmas. Such a biased vision of language can poorly dispose teachers and students of English. U.N Singh (2017) observes that sometimes teachers, teacher-trainers, textbooks writers and many teacher education programmes overemphasise the formal aspects of language while neglecting the social nature of language, that language is for interaction. Sparing the use of literature to teach L2 (Prasad, 2017; Sinha, 2014) and teacher-centred curriculum (Mangalaprathaban, 2013) is perhaps the consequences of such wrong notions and assumptions policymakers, educators and administrators have.

Lack of employability skills due to poor language skills is indicated as a drawback in many curricula (*India Skills Report*, 2019; Sasirekha et al., 2018). Jain (2018) affirms that unemployability is linked to a lack of English language proficiency. Good communication skills are necessary for recruitment, growth, and professional effectiveness (S. Singh, 2014). People who have proficiency in the English language access a large number of jobs and are seen holding high positions in many National and International organisations and companies (Sebastian, 2018). In this regard, Vijay (2014) states that the syllabi, in many cases, are not realistic and relevant to learners' career expectations.

Studies have explored the ELT curriculum to find out what is lacking in the Indian ELT programmes that are meant to equip language teachers. Jha (2017) explored the most acclaimed ELT programmes in the world and compared the curricular components that make a globally ideal ELT program. The researcher found TESOL to be the most preferred ELT programme internationally. However, only four percent of the curricular components internationally in demand were found in MA English, the most acclaimed Indian ELT programme. In yet another paper by the same author (Jha, 2018), the gap between the most acclaimed ELT programmes in the world and the Indian ELT programmes was explored. He identified the curricular components of all these 29 programmes and found the following regarding the Indian English programmes: Indian ELT programmes lack 48 percent of those curricular components; Indian ELT programmes are oriented more towards English literature rather than the English language; the average inclusion of the curricular components of these world-renowned programmes in the Indian ELT is only 11.42 percentage; curriculum development, syllabus design, theories of second language acquisition, teaching four macro skill using authentic materials, second language research methodology which is the backbone an ELT programme is present in Indian ELT programmes only by four percentage; absence of teaching practicum and Methods of ELT present in Indian ELT programme by twenty-five percent.

Discussion and Conclusions

The review aimed to understand the problems and challenges in English Language Teaching in India. The answer to the first research question, '*What recurring challenges and problems in ELT in India*

are reported' was summarised under Schwab's five curriculum commonplaces, namely, subject matter, learner, teacher, milieu, and curriculum. The second research question was *What do these challenges and problems reveal about the status of ELT in India?*

Schwab's Curriculum commonplace frame work says that when portions are selected from a discipline for a subject matter to be taught in a classroom, it should be in the interests of the needs and abilities of the children and should be good or best or satisfying to the learners. He further says that the curriculum material should be such that it should make the student competent. The findings from this review reveal that poorly prepared L2 teaching materials and obsolete and inefficient methods of teaching L2 are the major subject matter-related barriers to ELT in many schools and colleges in India. The findings imply that the very process of the preparation of curriculum material and its nature and content in many schools and colleges needs to be aligned with the needs and abilities of the learners. Secondly, teachers are important mediators of learning for students, according to Schwab. Their knowledge, beliefs, capabilities, lack of capabilities, attitude, background, relationships to superiors and to others, biases and political affiliations impact the implementation of the curriculum. The review found that teacher incompetency in terms of knowledge of methods and content is the biggest teacher-centred challenge in ELT in many institutions. The findings point to the lack of effectiveness of teacher training programmes in many institutions.

The third component in Schwab's frame work notes that the curriculum should be learner centric. Learners' age, knowledge level, readiness to learn, difficulty and ease of learning, aspirations and anxieties should be considered to make it suitable to the needs of the learners. The review found that many students do not really recognise and appreciate the utility of L2 learning and that a considerable number of students are demotivated to learn L2. It was found that the subject matter was, in many cases, not aligned with the needs and abilities of the learners. The ELT curriculum in India, therefore, must become more learner-centric for it to be appealing to the learners.

Fourthly, the review found that the disparities in education between the urban and rural populations, the cultural diversity in classrooms and inadequate policies and infrastructure as the major contextual barriers. According to Schwab, the classroom, the school, the wider community, the student's family, the neighbourhood, religion, and culture constitute the context in which the students learn. The review suggests that contextual barriers fundamentally affect ELT, and hence, there needs to be a radical change in the ELT learning environment.

The fifth set of findings from the review shows that many ELT curricula in India are inadequate due to their teacher-centred approach, content that is not envisaged for the development of communication skills in the learners, and their inability to make students employable by developing communication skills. According to Schwab, the final curriculum is a balanced combination of all four components. Inadequacies in the ELT curriculum, it can be argued, result from the inefficient and well-rounded policies that govern the process of ELT curriculum-making in the country in general.

(This is an original publication and has not been published elsewhere and has not been submitted elsewhere, or is under review in any other journal.)

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